

Rac-1ae

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-108-s-rac-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0831
Vial:	104	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 2 108 s rac
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	8.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/31/2021 12:00:48 AM CST		
Date Processed:	8/31/2021 8:49:26 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.479	7649585	49.90	1186949
2	6.636	7678894	50.10	955320

Asy-1ae

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-109-4-s-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0831
Vial:	105	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 2 109 4 s
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	8.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/31/2021 12:14:41 AM CST		
Date Processed:	8/31/2021 8:51:22 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.483	280651	3.26	41359
2	6.636	8338747	96.74	1037336